

Annex B

Programme Disaster Relief in CSDP Context Course

ESDC activity no 22-23/44/3

Bucharest, 18-21 July 2023

- Hotel Sheraton, Platinum Conference Room

Date/Time Bucharest (EET / GMT+3)	Intervention / Panel	Speakers
Day 1 - Tuesday, 18/07/2023		
09.00-09.45	<i>Arrival & registration</i>	
10.00-11.00	<i>Opening speeches</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Col. Ștefan-Claudiu Chindriș, Commander (Rector) of "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" Police Academy • Police Quaestor Cătălin Andruș, PhD, Director of the National College of Home Affairs (CNAI) & course co-director • Col. Orlin Nikolov, PhD, Director of Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence Sofia (CMDR COE) & course co-director • Col. Marius Dogeanu, Head of General Directorate for Civil Protection • Mr. Valentin Katrandzhiev, PhD (Bulgarian Diplomatic Institute) • Mr. Georgios Kapogiannis, ESDC Training Manager <p style="text-align: right;">Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu, PhD - CNAI</p>
11.00-11.30	<i>Official photo / Coffee break</i>	
11.30-12.30	The EU-wide strategic framework on CSDP in the context of Euro-Atlantic evolutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Iulian Chifu, PhD, The Romanian Prime Minister Counsellor for Security <p style="text-align: right;">Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu, PhD - CNAI</p>
12.30-13.30	<i>Lunch break – Avalon Restaurant, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
13.30-14.15	ESDC in support of the EU integrated approach. Presentation of the National College of Home Affairs Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Police Quaestor Cătălin Andruș, PhD, Director of the National College of Home Affairs (CNAI) & course director • Mr. Georgios Kapogiannis, ESDC Training Manager <p style="text-align: right;">Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu, PhD - CNAI</p>
14.15-15.45	The EU integrated approach to disaster management: structures, tools and policies for disaster prevention, preparedness, relief and post-disaster rehabilitation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Ionuț Homeag, Leadership Team - Emergency Response Coordination Centre / DG European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG ECHO)

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	EU Civil Protection Mechanism / Emergency Response Coordination Centre	Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
15.45-16.15	<i>Coffee break</i>	
16.15-17.15	EU support in CSDP context in the benefit of third countries, with focus on Eastern Partnership countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Simion Costea, PhD – the former project manager DG Near Neighborhood and Enlargement Negotiations / European Commission • Mr. Ciprian Năstăsoiu, DG INTPA Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
17.15-17.30	Tour de table / presentation of the trainees	Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
18.00-19.30	Welcome cocktail hosted by CNAI <i>Location: hotel lobby</i>	
Day 2 – Wednesday, 19/07/2023		
09.00-10.30	STRATCOM in disaster relief: the media's role in disasters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mrs. Alina Bârgăoanu, PhD, Professor and Dean, National University for Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations • Mrs. Flavia Durach, PhD, Associate Professor, National University for Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations • Mr. Simion Costea, PhD – the former project manager DG Near Neighborhood and Enlargement Negotiations / European Commission Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu, PhD, CNAI
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.00	Natural disasters in the context of global security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Valentin Katrandzhiev, PhD (Bulgarian Diplomatic Institute) Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
12.00-13.00	<i>Lunch break – Avalon Restaurant, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
13.00-14.00	Building resilience. Big Data in Disaster Management Critical infrastructure protection, cyber security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Dan Cîmpean, Director of National Cyber Security Directorate • Mr. Nicolae Merlă, Ministry of Internal Affairs - National Coordination Centre for Critical Infrastructure Protection • Mr. Adrian Victor VEVERA, PhD, Managing Director of the National Institute for Research and Development in Informatics Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI

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14.00-15.00	EU as international humanitarian assistance / relief actor. Coordination by and with NATO and UN / UNHCR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Claudiu Zoicaș, NATO HQ • Mrs. Kylie Alcoba Wright (SNR Operations Manager) & Mrs. Ana Grozea (Protection Associate) - UNHCR Romania Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
15.00-15.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.30-16.25	Education and training - an important part of maintaining capabilities for the EU's disaster response and humanitarian assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Doncho Doychev, PhD, Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence Sofia (CMDR COE) • Mr. Alin Lungu, Deputy Director of the Research and Training Department from the Euro-Atlantic Resilience Centre Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
16.25-16.30	<i>Break</i>	
16.30-17.30	EU military role in disaster relief. Interoperability between civilian and military capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LTC Ciprian Ignat, PhD, Associate Professor, National Defense University "CAROL I", Security and Defense Faculty • Mr. Doncho Doychev, PhD, Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence Sofia (CMDR COE) Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
Day 3 – Thursday, 20/07/2023		
09.00-10.00	Cooperation and synergies between emergency situations and public order systems for impact management in disaster relief situations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Ștefan Săvulescu (OF-7), General Director of the General Directorate for Operational Management of the Ministry of Internal Affairs • Mr. Daniel Vasile, Euro-Atlantic Resilience Centre Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
10.00-11.00	The role of NGOs in Disaster Relief: The experience of the Romanian Red Cross and its coordination with GOs. SMURD Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mr. Daniel MODOACĂ - Head of Department for Emergency Situations and Disaster Management – National Society of Red Cross Romania • Mrs. Charlotte Nicol, Head of Mission to Romania - International Committee of the Red Cross • Mrs. Ioana Mirela Daramus, MD, MSc, Programs Director - Foundation for SMURD's Activity Coordinator Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
11.00-11.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	

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11.30-12.00	Briefing on the exercise / study visit concerning the Emergency Management in Disaster Relief	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lt. Timotei DEDU - Department of Emergency Situations (DSU) / General Directorate for Operational Management (DGMO) representative Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
12.00-13.00	<i>Lunch break – Avalon Restaurant, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
13.00-14.00	<i>Travel from Sheraton Hotel to CNCCI Ciolpani</i>	
14.00-17.00	Emergency Management in Disaster Relief – Exercise / study visit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Centre for Coordination and Intervention Management (CNCCI) Ciolpani / National Centre for the Improvement of Emergency Management Training Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
17.00-18.00	<i>Travel from CNCCI Ciolpani to Sheraton Hotel</i>	
19.00-22.00	Official Dinner hosted by National College of Home Affairs UNESCO Cultural Center Mihai Eminescu - Romanian Painting Exhibition <i>Location: Arizona & Colorado salon, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
Day 4 – Friday, 21/07/2023		
09.00-10.00	Using of M&S and creating of technical architecture in support of Decision Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Col. Orlin Nikolov, PhD, Director of Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence Sofia (CMDR COE) & course co-director Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
10.00-10.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
10.30-11.50	The role and structure of the Emergency System, the importance of international collaboration and civil - military cooperation in emergency situations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dr. Raed Arafat, State Secretary, Head of the Department of Emergency Situations, Ministry of Internal Affairs, Romania Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
11.50-12.00	<i>Break</i>	
12.00-13.00	Closing remarks, survey, Handling of Certificates, photo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dr. Raed Arafat, State Secretary, Head of the Department of Emergency Situations, Ministry of Internal Affairs, Romania Police Quaestor Cătălin Andruș, PhD, Director of the National College of Home Affairs (CNAI) & course co-director Col. Orlin Nikolov, PhD, Director of Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence Sofia (CMDR COE) & course co-director Mr. Georgios Kapogiannis, ESDC Training Manager Moderator: Mr. Bogdan Marinescu , PhD - CNAI
13.00-14.00	<i>Lunch break – Avalon Restaurant, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
Departure of participants		

